

an appropriate check, 3 to 5 m long, spaced 20 cm within rows and 20 cm between rows. Ten hills were inoculated in each test row at about panicle initiation stage (60–70 days after seeding). Disease observations on the test entries, based on a 0 to 9 scale, were recorded at 3 weeks after inoculation and 10 days after flowering.

In greenhouse tests, the plants were grown individually in plastic pots 15.2 × 15.2 cm (6 × 6 in.) and were inoculated at around the panicle initiation stage. A minimum of three replicates were maintained for each test entry. For pathogen establishment, the inoculated plants were placed in humid chambers (RH = > 95%, maintained from 1600 to 0800 hours the next day) for 5 days, then transferred to glasshouse

benches. Overhead sprinklers were used from 1000 to 1500 hours daily to facilitate further disease development. Disease observations were recorded at 14 days after inoculation at 25 to 33°C, or at 21 days after inoculation at 22 to 30°C, based on the 0–9 disease severity scale.

In the 1975–77 wet season, about 2,000 test entries in the National Screening Nursery and the International Sheath Blight Screening Nursery were screened in the field and about 500 entries of the Assam Rice Collection were evaluated in the glasshouse. Those entries found tolerant in the field were also critically reevaluated in the glasshouse.

In our 3-year study no variety or selection was resistant to the sheath blight pathogen. But certain entries had low disease incidence; they had a few restricted lesions on the lower leaf sheaths and the basal stem regions. The entries having tolerance (disease score < 5) are listed in the table. Several of the tolerant semidwarf selections derive from gall midge-resistance breeding programs (e.g., progeny belonging to the series RP974, RP975, IR2071, etc.). Out of 500 ARC entries tested in the glasshouse, 4 rices — ARC 15762, ARC 18119, ARC 18275, and ARC 18545 — were tolerant of sheath blight.

Varieties and selections that had low disease scores in field and glasshouse tests at AICRIP, India, during 1975–1977.

Designation	Disease score		
	Field test		Glasshouse test 1977
	Wet season 1975	Wet season 1976	
<i>IRSHBN test entries</i>			
B 9c-Md-3-3	3	—	5
IR789-98-2	5	—	5
IR1103-15-8	5	—	5
IR1910-472 P	5	—	5
Guyana Sel. 60-283	5	—	5
IR2071-588-4-4	5	—	5
IR2071-588-4-5-1	3	5	6
IR2798-88-32	5	5	6
IR2843-26-3-2	5	5	6
BR-4-30-51-2	5	—	6
Remadja	5	—	5
Sigadis	5	—	5
Pankaj (resistant check)	5	—	5
<i>National screening entries</i>			
OR 42-10	5	5	8
RP 974-25-4-3-1	5	3	3
CU1 6475	5	1	—
CR 129-120	5	5	5
PAU 21-88-5	5	5	4
CR 149-3295-4-205	5	3	—
IR2071-176-1-2-1	5	3	—
IR2071-747-6-3-2	5	3	—
RP975-109-2	5	1	5
RP975-121-6-1-1	5	—	3
RP975-25-4-3-1	5	3	3

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Resurgence-inducing insecticides as a tool in field screening of rices against the brown planthopper

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Rice varieties and selections are usually screened for resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) in the greenhouse where 7- to 14-day-old seedlings are evaluated by the seedbox technique. This method has effectively identified highly resistant material but has been less effective in identifying strains with moderate and field resistance. At IRRI and in Sri Lanka, the reactions of some varieties have varied distinctly between the greenhouse and the field. Extensive field screening should precede the release of a variety. But several years may be required to obtain reliable data because BPH are distributed unevenly within a field and populations are often too low to evaluate. Even when screening is done in so-called *hot spots*, the pest's unpredictability can cause high expenditures in money, labor, land, and time.

The use of insecticide application as a technique in inducing BPH resurgence

was developed to provide evenly distributed and high-BPH field populations at about 80 days after transplanting. In insecticide evaluation studies we have identified insecticides that cause BPH resurgence. The synthetic pyrethroid decamethrin, as well as methyl parathion and diazinon, effectively promote resurgences (see table). The synthetic pyrethroid cypermethrin (NRDC 149), azinphos ethyl, and carbofuran also cause resurgence (the latter may be effective only where the BPH has developed resistance to the insecticide). In India, mephosfolan, quinalphos, phorate, and the combination of dimecron + nuvan have been reported to cause resurgences. Foliar sprays induce resurgences more effectively than granular formulations.

Our field screening procedure for BPH resistance starts with the planting of three or more border rows of a line, such as IR1917-3-17, which is susceptible to BPH but resistant to tungro virus (see figure). The borders are planted across each end of the test entries. Depending on seed availability, from 1 to 4 rows — each 5 m long — of the test entries are planted with 1 row of a susceptible check variety between each entry. The border rows are sprayed at a low rate — about 100 g

Effect of foliar sprays on brown planthopper (BPH) population and damage in upland rice (variety Kinanda).^a IRRI, 1976 wet season.

Insecticide ^b	BPH population (no./10 linear-m row) 94 DS ^c	Resurgence ratio (x:1) ^d	Hopperburn (%) 117 DS
Decamethrin	6,733 a	16.4	100
Methyl parathion	2,468 a	6.0	75
Diazinon	1,919 ab	4.1	55
BPMC	178 c	0.4	1
Perthane	29 d	0.1	0
Control	411 bc	-	4

^a In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^b Insecticides were applied three times at 49, 72, and 94 days after seeding (DS) at 0.75 kg a.i./ha.

^c The planthopper counts at 94 DS were made before the third application.

^d Resurgence ratio = $\frac{\text{number of brown planthoppers in insecticide treatment}}{\text{number of brown planthoppers in untreated control}}$

Field plot layout used in the field evaluation of rice for brown planthopper resistance IRRI, 1978.

active ingredient/ha. The spray is directed at the canopy. Plants are sprayed at 10-day intervals beginning at 30 days after transplanting. Plant damage is first rated when the adjacent susceptible check variety is killed, then is rated at 1-week intervals until increase in damage ceases. The extent of damage as based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice and

the percentage of hopperburned plants are then recorded. For additional information on BPH buildup, insects are counted at regular intervals throughout the crop season. Varieties with moderate levels of field resistance are easier to detect with this technique than with the greenhouse method. \mathcal{W}

Varietal resistance to striped rice borer *Chilo suppressalis*

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One hundred and twenty-seven rice varieties and lines were evaluated to determine the correlation among percentage of infested tillers, larval

number, and larval weight.

Twenty days after seeding, plants were transplanted in two replications of six hills (2 plants/hill) in a net house. Thirty 10- × 12-cm dishes containing 200 larvae on straw were placed in the middle of the net house so that moths could emerge and infest the varieties.

After 50 days, all stems of each rice were dissected, the larvae and infested tillers were counted, and larval weights were determined.

The percentage of infested tillers correlated positively with both the number of larvae and the larval weights in all rices (Fig. 1, 2).

In varieties with a low number of infested tillers, there was a high correlation between infested tillers and number of larvae, but in varieties with high infestation (more than 80%), number of infested tillers did not correlate significantly with number of larvae.

In moderately resistant varieties (less than 80% infested tillers), the percentage of infested tillers correlated significantly with larval weights. As larval numbers increased, larval lengths and body weights were reduced proportionately. The resistant check IR747 had 51% tiller infestation, but the larvae that fed on it had significantly lower body weights and numbers. \mathcal{W}

1. Relationship between percentage of infested tillers and number of striped rice borers in rices evaluated in the screenhouse. Suweon, Korea.

2. Relationship between percentage of infested tillers and larval weight of striped rice borers in rices evaluated in the screenhouse. Suweon, Korea.